

Why Michelson-Morley Experiments Give Null Result

Henok Tadesse
Email: entkidmt@yahoo.com

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Abstract

Many researchers and physicists, including renowned scientists, have long questioned the foundations of relativity theory, which are the two postulates: the principle of relativity and the constancy of the speed of light, and their consequences. However, what exactly is wrong with relativity theory has eluded researchers for more than a century. This paper reveals the mystery of why the Michelson-Morley experiments always give null fringe shifts, contrary to other experimental evidences of absolute motion, such as the Silvertooth experiment and the Marinov experiment. A new theory/model of the speed of light is formulated as follows. The effect of absolute motion of the Michelson-Morley device is just to cause *an apparent change in the time of emission of light from the source*. Thus, both the longitudinal and transverse light beams are delayed or advanced equally, *by the same amount*, in which case no fringe shift will occur. The center of the light wave fronts is always the same point *relative to the observer/detector* between the moments of light emission and light detection. The center of the light wave fronts is fixed at the point where the source was *relative to the detector* at the moment of emission and is always fixed in the reference frame of the detector (relative to the detector) and is therefore always co-moving with the observer/detector. The speed of light is constant c relative to the center of the light wave fronts, and therefore it is always constant relative to the observer. The mystery behind the Michelson-Morley experiment is that it is impossible to detect absolute motion from the interference pattern formed by light beams originating from a *single* source! Therefore, the key to detect absolute motion by using the Michelson-Morley kind experiments would be by interference of light beams from two *independent* sources. Such hypothetical experiment would give thousands of fringe shifts. However, such experiment is not possible with current technology, because the coherence time/length of light is very short, and because it is nearly impossible to tune the frequencies of two independent laser sources to be equal to within, say, 0.1 to 1 Hz to get any fringe patterns stable enough to see if a fringe shift occurs with change in orientation of the modified MM device in space.

Introduction

The null result of the Michelson-Morley experiments, both the classical and modern, are considered to be the single most important experimental evidence for the principle and theory of relativity. On the other hand, experimental, theoretical and logical counter-evidences against relativity theory are accumulating from time to time [1][2]. The Silvertooth experiment and the Marinov experiment have detected large first order effects of absolute motion. Therefore, the problem of whether absolute motion exists and can be detected is still an unsettled problem nearly one hundred years after the birth of Albert Einstein's relativity theory.

Many researchers and physicists, including renowned scientists, have questioned the foundations of relativity theory, which are the two postulates: the principle of relativity and the constancy of the speed of light, and their consequences such as time dilation and length contraction. Researchers have long known

that there is something wrong with relativity theory. However, what exactly is wrong with relativity theory has eluded physicists and researchers for more than a century. This paper reveals the mystery of why the Michelson-Morley experiments give null results, despite other experiments that have detected absolute motion.

A new theory of the Michelson-Morley experiment

A new theory of the speed of light is formulated as follows. The effect of absolute motion on the Michelson-Morley device is just to cause *a change in the time delay* of the longitudinal and transverse light beams *by the same amount*, in which case no fringe shift will occur. Both the longitudinal and the transverse light beams are delayed or advanced *equally*, so no fringe shift is expected. The mystery behind the Michelson-Morley experiment is that it is impossible to detect absolute motion from the interference pattern of light beams originating from a *single* source!

Thus, the effect of absolute motion on the Michelson-Morley experiment (MMX) is just to create an additional a time delay (or time advance) of light detection at the observer/detector compared to the time delay when the MM apparatus is at rest. This additional time delay (or time advance) is determined solely by the *direct* distance D (Fig.1) between the detector/observer and the light source and angle Θ *at the moment of emission* and the magnitude and direction of absolute velocity.

Fig. 1

According to the new theory, the effect of absolute motion of the Michelson-Morley device is to create an additional delay of τ in all the light beams reaching the observer. That is, if the light coming to the detector *directly* from the source undergoes an additional time delay of τ due to absolute motion, then the light beams coming to the detector after reflection from mirrors co-moving with the observer/detector will also be delayed by the same amount τ !

To restate the above clearly, consider three light beams reaching the observer, one coming directly from the source and the other two coming after reflection from mirrors co-moving with the observer. Note that this does not mean that there must be a light beam actually coming to the detector directly from the source necessarily. For example, light directly coming to the observer could be blocked by placing a plate between the source and the observer/detector. *In order to determine how absolute motion affects light coming to the detector after reflecting from the mirror, we determine how absolute motion would affect (delay or advance) light coming to the observer directly from the source. If the light coming to the detector directly from the source is delayed by τ , then light coming to the observer after reflection from a mirror co-moving with the observer will also be delayed by the same amount τ !*

Absolute motion causes equal delays of all the three light beams reaching the observer/detector. Thus, no fringe shift will occur in the Michelson-Morley experiment because both the longitudinal and transverse light beams will be affected identically/equally by absolute motion of the apparatus. *Both* of the light beams are delayed by τ compared to the case when the MM apparatus is at rest. This is why, according to the new theory, the Michelson-Morley experiment is not capable of detecting absolute motion. This is unlike ether theory which predicts a fringe shift.

To formulate the new theory, consider an observer moving relative to the absolute reference frame, (Fig.2). At first we analyze this experiment classically as follows.

Fig. 2

Let the light source emit a short light pulse at the time instant $t = 0$. At the moment of emission, the observer is at point O in the absolute reference frame and moving with velocity V_{abs} to the right, as shown. The point of light emission is at distance D and angle θ relative to the observer/detector, at the moment of emission. Let the observer detect the light pulse at point O'. To determine D' and Δ we proceed classically as follows.

During the time interval that the light moves from point S to point O', the observer moves from point O to point O'. That is:

$$\frac{D'}{c} = \frac{\Delta}{V_{abs}}$$

From the triangle SOO'

$$D' = \sqrt{D^2 + \Delta^2 - 2D\Delta \cos(180^\circ - \theta)}$$

Therefore, given D , θ and V_{abs} , D' and Δ can be determined from the last two equations.

Combining the last two equations :

$$D'^2 \left(1 - \frac{V_{abs}^2}{c^2}\right) - D' \left(2D \frac{V_{abs}}{c}\right) \cos\theta - D^2 = 0 \quad . . . \quad (1)$$

from which D' , and then Δ are determined.

$$D' = \frac{-b \pm \sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}}{2a} = \frac{\left(2D \frac{V_{abs}}{c}\right) \cos\theta + \sqrt{\left(2D \frac{V_{abs}}{c}\right) \cos\theta)^2 + 4\left(1 - \frac{V_{abs}^2}{c^2}\right) D^2}}{2\left(1 - \frac{V_{abs}^2}{c^2}\right)}$$

$$\Rightarrow D' = \frac{\left(D \frac{V_{abs}}{c}\right) \cos\theta + D \sqrt{1 - \frac{V_{abs}^2}{c^2} \sin^2\theta}}{\left(1 - \frac{V_{abs}^2}{c^2}\right)} \quad \quad (2)$$

$$\Rightarrow D' = D \left(1 + \frac{V_{abs}}{c} \cos\theta\right) \quad , \quad for \quad V_{abs} \ll c \quad \quad (3)$$

Absolute motion of the observer causes an additional time delay of the light, given by:

$$\tau = \frac{D'}{c} - \frac{D}{c} = \frac{D \left(1 + \frac{V_{abs}}{c} \cos\theta\right)}{c} - \frac{D}{c} = \frac{D}{c} \frac{V_{abs}}{c} \cos\theta \quad . . . \quad (4)$$

A new interpretation

There is nothing new in the classical analysis we have done so far. What is new is the interpretation we are going to give next. Suppose that we add a mirror that is co-moving with the observer to the above experiment (Fig.3). Now we have two light beams reaching the observer/detector: one light beam directly from the source and the other light beam after reflection from the co-moving mirror. We have shown that the light beam coming to the observer/detector directly from the source is additionally delayed by an amount τ given by equation (4) because of observer's motion . The new finding is that, unconventionally, *the light beam reaching the observer after reflecting from the mirror will also be additionally delayed by the same amount τ* . This is the century-old mystery behind the null result of the Michelson-Morley experiment. At this point the reader should note the distinction that this is not even in accordance with

ether theory. The ether doesn't exist but absolute motion does exist. Not surprisingly, the two have always been (wrongly) considered to be synonymous.

Therefore, in the conventional Michelson-Morley experiment both the longitudinal and transverse light beams are delayed (or advanced) equally/identically due to absolute motion, therefore no fringe shift is expected.

The new theory proposed in this paper is that the effect of absolute motion of the observer is just to create an apparent change in the moment of emission of light. Thus, if the moment of light emission is apparently delayed by τ , then all light beams reaching the observer will be delayed by the same amount, whether it is the light coming to the observer directly from the source or light coming to the observer after reflecting from a co-moving mirror.

The effect of absolute motion of the Michelson-Morley interferometer is just to cause *an apparent change in the time of emission of light from the source*. Thus, both the longitudinal and transverse light beams of the conventional Michelson-Morley experiment are delayed or advanced *by the same amount*, in which case no fringe shift will occur. Both the longitudinal and the transverse light beams are delayed or advanced *equally*, so no fringe shift is expected. The center of the light wave fronts is always at the same point *relative to the observer/detector* between the moments of light emission and light detection. *The center of the light wave fronts is fixed at the point where the source was relative to the detector at the moment of emission and is always fixed in the reference frame of the detector and is therefore always co-moving with the detector. The speed of light is constant relative to the center of the light wave fronts, and therefore it is always constant relative to the observer.*

Fig. 3

A hypothetical Michelson-Morley experiment

From the above analysis we have seen that it is impossible to detect absolute motion by using conventional Michelson-Morley kind interferometer experiments. This is because absolute motion of the Michelson-Morley device will not cause any *change in the time difference* of two light rays originating from a *single* source, taking different paths to reach the point of detection. The effect of absolute motion

is only to cause *equal time changes* (time delay or time advance) to *both* the light rays, which will not cause any fringe shift.

The key to detect absolute motion by using the Michelson-Morley kind experiments would be by interference of light from two *independent* sources. However, such experiment is not feasible with current technology because the coherence time/length of light is very short and because it is impossible to tune the frequency of two laser sources to be equal to within, say, 0.1Hz to get any ‘stable’ fringe patterns. In this paper we analyze such experiment and show that it would give thousands of fringe shifts when the orientation of the device in space is changed. Unfortunately, this is only a hypothetical experiment because it is practically impossible to realize. Since rotating the device and observing the fringe positions can take, say, at least 30 seconds, we would need laser sources with coherence time of at least 30 seconds. One might ask: then why analyze an experiment that is known to be practically impossible? We do this to clearly reveal the mystery that has eluded physicists for one century.

We will first consider the effect of absolute motion on the light beam from S2.

Fig. 4

It can be shown that the effect of absolute motion on the light beam from S2 is negligible because the position of S2 relative to the observer is orthogonal to the direction of absolute velocity. This can be shown by substituting $\theta = 90^0$ in equation (2), which will give:

$$D' = \frac{\left(D \frac{V_{abs}}{c}\right) \cos\theta + D \sqrt{1 - \frac{V_{abs}^2}{c^2}} \sin^2\theta}{\left(1 - \frac{V_{abs}^2}{c^2}\right)} = \frac{D \sqrt{1 - \frac{V_{abs}^2}{c^2}}}{\left(1 - \frac{V_{abs}^2}{c^2}\right)}$$

Therefore,

$$\tau = \frac{D'}{c} - \frac{D}{c} = \frac{\frac{D \sqrt{1 - \frac{V_{abs}^2}{c^2}}}{\left(1 - \frac{V_{abs}^2}{c^2}\right)}}{c} - \frac{D}{c} = \frac{D}{c} \left(\frac{\sqrt{1 - \frac{V_{abs}^2}{c^2}}}{\left(1 - \frac{V_{abs}^2}{c^2}\right)} - 1 \right)$$

$$\Rightarrow \tau \cong \frac{D}{c} (1 - 1) \cong 0, \text{ for } V_{abs} \ll c$$

Next we consider the effect of absolute motion on the light beam from S1. The additional time delay induced by absolute motion of the light beam reaching the detector after reflecting from the mirror is given by equation (4):

$$\tau = \frac{D}{c} \frac{V_{abs}}{c} \cos\theta, \text{ for } V_{abs} \ll c$$

Therefore, the time difference between the longitudinal and orthogonal light beams will be:

$$\tau = \frac{D}{\frac{\sin\theta}{c}} \frac{V_{abs}}{c} \cos\theta = \frac{D}{c} \frac{V_{abs}}{c} \frac{1}{\tan\theta}$$

For example, if $D = 1 \text{ m} = 0.001 \text{ km}$, $\theta = 30^0$, $V_{abs} = 390 \text{ km/s}$, $c = 300000 \text{ km/s}$

$$\tau = \frac{D}{c} \frac{V_{abs}}{c} \frac{1}{\tan\theta} = \frac{0.001}{300000} \frac{390}{300000} \frac{1}{\tan 30^0} = 7.5 * 10^{-12} \text{ s}$$

Let the wavelength of the laser light used be 600 nm.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{the fringe shift caused by absolute motion} &= \frac{c \tau}{\text{wavelength}} \\ &= \frac{3 * 10^8 * 7.5 * 10^{-12} \text{ s}}{600 * 10^{-9}} = 3750 \text{ fringes} \end{aligned}$$

Contrast this with the almost null result of the Michelson-Morley experiments!

Unfortunately, such experiment is nearly impossible because the coherence length/coherence time of laser sources is too short and it is practically impossible to tune the frequencies of two laser sources to be equal to within, say, 0.1 to 1 Hz, to get any ‘stable’ and visible interference fringes. Even if it was possible to tune the two laser frequencies to be equal to within, say, 10 Hz the experiment would be feasible. Although the fringes would be moving in this case, this would be a feasible experiment given the large number of fringe shifts predicted when the orientation of the apparatus is changed. As already noted, the coherence time of the light should be at least about 30 seconds, the time needed to rotate the device and observe changes in fringe positions.

Moving source experiments

The new model of (absolute) motion and the speed of light gives a straight forward explanation of moving source experiments. Assume an observer that is at absolute rest. A light source is moving relative to the observer (and therefore relative to the absolute reference frame). According to the new theory, the effect of *absolute motion of the observer* is just to create an apparent change in the time of emission of light from the source. This apparent change in time of emission is determined by the absolute velocity of the observer and the position (distance and direction) of the light source relative to the observer *at the moment of emission*. Since in this case the observer is at rest (zero absolute velocity), with only the source moving, there is no apparent change in the moment of light emission. Therefore, the time delay of light between emission and detection is determined by the distance between the observer and the source *at the moment of emission*.

$$\text{time delay between emission and detection} = \frac{D}{c}$$

Since only the position (distance) of the source from the observer at the moment of emission and the absolute velocity of the observer (in this case zero) determine the time delay, the velocity of the light source is irrelevant, confirming the independence of the speed of light from the velocity of the source.

Moving observer experiments

Imagine a light source at that is at absolute rest. (the motion/velocity of the source is irrelevant, we are assuming it just for clarity). The light source emits a short light pulse at the instant $t = 0$. At the moment of emission, the observer is at distance D from the source and moving with absolute velocity V_{abs} to the right (Fig. 5).

Fig.5

This is the case of $\Theta = 0$ in Fig.2. Therefore, from equation (2):

$$\begin{aligned} \Rightarrow D' &= \frac{\left(D \frac{V_{abs}}{c}\right) \cos\theta + D \sqrt{1 - \frac{V_{abs}^2}{c^2}} \sin^2\theta}{\left(1 - \frac{V_{abs}^2}{c^2}\right)} \\ \Rightarrow D' &= \frac{\left(D \frac{V_{abs}}{c}\right) + D}{\left(1 - \frac{V_{abs}^2}{c^2}\right)} = \frac{D \left(1 + \frac{V_{abs}}{c}\right)}{\left(1 - \frac{V_{abs}^2}{c^2}\right)} = \frac{D}{1 - \frac{V_{abs}}{c}} \end{aligned}$$

The apparent time delay of emission caused by observer's absolute motion is:

$$\tau = \frac{D'}{c} - \frac{D}{c} = \frac{\frac{D}{1 - \frac{V_{abs}}{c}}}{c} - \frac{D}{c} = \frac{D}{c} \left(\frac{1}{1 - \frac{V_{abs}}{c}} - 1 \right) = \frac{D}{c} \frac{V_{abs}}{c - V_{abs}}$$

In this case, τ is the apparent change (delay) in the time of light emission for the moving observer. Therefore, in order to determine the moment of light detection, we consider this apparent time delay of emission.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{moment of light detection} &= \tau + \frac{D}{c} = \frac{D}{c} \frac{V_{abs}}{c - V_{abs}} + \frac{D}{c} \\ &= \frac{D}{c} \left(\frac{V_{abs}}{c - V_{abs}} + 1 \right) = \frac{D}{c - V_{abs}} \end{aligned}$$

This agrees with moving observer experiments.

Stellar aberration

Suppose that at $t = 0$ the light source emits light from point S in the absolute reference frame. At the moment of emission ($t = 0$), the observer is at point O, moving with absolute velocity V_{abs} to the right (Fig. 6).

Let the moving observer detect the light at the point O'. As already described, the position (distance and direction) of the point of light emission (or the center of the wave fronts) *relative to the observer* at the moment of emission (line OS) is the same as position of the point of light emission (the center of the light wave fronts) at the moment of light detection (line O'S').

We can see that the two lines OS and O'S' are parallel and have equal lengths. Therefore, whereas an observer at rest at point O' will see the light as coming from the point S, the moving observer sees the light as coming from S'.

Fig. 6

The Arago and the Airy star light refraction and aberration experiments

The Arago experiment was perhaps the first experiment that encountered the paradoxical nature of the speed of light, which would confound physics for centuries to come. Francois Arago set out to test (actually to 'confirm', as he was an advocate of emission theory) if the speed of light depended on the velocity of the stars. For this, he observed the refraction of light from different stars. He found that the lights from all the stars were refracted by the same amount, in the same way, showing that the speed of light was independent of the velocity of the star. Then, naturally he decided to test if the speed of light depended on the velocity of the observer. For this, he observed the refraction of light from a star at different times of the year, in order to utilize variations in the Earth's orbital velocity. To his surprise, he found no evidence that refraction of light coming from the star varied at different times of the year, showing that the speed of light did not depend on the velocity of the observer either. Thus was born the light speed paradox.

Airy also did an experiment by using water filled telescopes to test if star light aberration angle differed from the aberration angle measured when observed by a telescope filled with air. He did not find any difference in the aberration angles in the two cases.

The new theory in this paper gives a straight forward explanation of the Arago and the Airy star light refraction and aberration experiments. *Light always approaches the observer with a constant velocity c, irrespective of the velocity of the observer and the velocity of the source. The only effect of the (absolute)*

motion of the observer is to create a change in the time of detection of light, which is irrelevant to the star light refraction and aberration experiments.

Conclusion

Nature has hidden its mystery in a safe place, and that is behind the null result of the Michelson-Morley experiment, derailing mainstream physics and everybody else who tried to find it, for over a century. The null result of the Michelson-Morley (MM) experiment can be considered as the single most important factor in the development and wide acceptance of the Special Relativity theory. For mainstream physics there is no more mystery and the Michelson-Morley experiment null result is just one evidence for the principle of relativity. Other researchers who have at least realized the failures of relativity theory and have been searching for alternative explanations have proposed numerous different ideas on why the MM experiment gave a null result, such as ether drag hypothesis. This paper has finally revealed the mystery of the Michelson-Morley experiment. How can the Michelson-Morley experiment give null result and absolute motion exist at the same time?!

Light is always emitted from its source with the velocity of the center of the light wave fronts equal to the (absolute) velocity of the observer. This means that the center of the wave fronts is always co-moving with the observer and therefore is at rest relative to the observer. The speed of light is constant c relative to the center of the wave fronts and therefore relative to the observer. This theory finally gives the correct explanation of the constancy of the speed of light relative to all observers. Albert Einstein was the first to realize and explicitly state the constancy of the speed of light. However, his interpretation of this principle of constancy of the speed of light, which is the Special Relativity theory, was wrong. This paper has finally revealed the correct interpretation. To account for absolute motion of the observer, light is emitted apparently earlier or later than the conventional time of light emission. This explains why an observer moving away from a light source detects the light later than if they remained at rest. The new theory can explain the Michelson-Morley experiment, moving source and moving observer experiments, stellar aberration and several other light speed experiments.

Glory be to God and His Mother, Our Lady Saint Virgin Mary

References

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